

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Audio Problems Detection on Sound Collections

Victor Badenas Crespo

Supervisor: Dmitry Bogdanov

Co-Supervisor: Pablo Alonso

June 2019

©Victor Badenas Crespo.

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Audio Problems Detection on Sound Collections

Victor Badenas Crespo

Supervisor: Dmitry Bogdanov

Co-Supervisor: Pablo Alonso

June 2019

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Objectives	1
1.2	Structure of the Report	2
2	State of the Art	3
2.1	Phase defects	3
2.2	Silence defects	4
2.3	Noise bursts defects	4
2.4	Humming defects	5
2.5	Click defects	5
2.6	Clipping defects	5
2.7	Bit depth defects	6
2.8	Sample Rate defects or Bandwidth defects	6
3	Methodology	7
3.1	Bit depth defects detection	7
3.2	Bandwidth defect detection	9
3.3	Low SNR defect detection	10
3.4	Manual annotation and Grid Search	12
4	Results	13
4.1	Clicks detection evaluation	14
4.2	Noise bursts detection evaluation	14

4.3	Saturation detection evaluation	15
4.4	Hum detection evaluation	15
4.5	Silence detection evaluation	16
4.6	BW problems detection evaluation	16
4.7	Bit depth problems evaluation	17
4.8	SNR problems evaluation	17
5	Conclusions	18
	List of Figures	20
	List of Tables	21
	Bibliography	22
A	First Appendix: Grid Search F-score, accuracy and recall	24

Acknowledgement

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to:

- My supervisor
- My co-supervisor
- My family
- My girlfriend

Abstract

This thesis is a first approach to creating and evaluating algorithms whose aim is to detect an unwanted feature in audio streams. Existing algorithms are evaluated and its parameters optimized for audio files without a specific length. These algorithms are used to detect defects such as clipping/saturation, Clicks, Noise Bursts, Hum, etc. Additionally, algorithms are developed in this thesis and also evaluated. To evaluate those results, a subset of Freesound is used after being annotated manually using scripts developed by the author. This ground truth is further used to evaluate the performance of the algorithms against it and is also used to sweep different values of the parameters available in the algorithms to find the parametrization that gives the best performance over a dataset of audios with multiple problems. For the evaluation dataset, the train set for the Kaggle Audio Tagging 2019 competition is used, as it is a collection of sounds with many problems to be detected. Due to some issues and time constraints, the results are not as satisfactory as previously expected.

Keywords: Audio Problems; Audio Tagging; Audio defects Detection;

Chapter 1

Introduction

Audio Problems refer to unwanted or undesired sound contained in an audio file. Many particular issues are considered undesirable, either for mixing purposes or for perceptual quality purposes. Quality of audio recordings can be both subjectively evaluated by perceptually detecting audio issues or can be also evaluated objectively by algorithms detecting patterns or specific features extracted from audio files. This thesis will be focused in the development and evaluation of the objective way to detect audio issues.

1.1 Objectives

The thesis will have three main objectives:

- The first one is to evaluate and tune existing algorithms, which are included in the Essentia library [1], which is a C++ library for audio analysis from MTG-UPF (Music Technology Group at Universitat Pompeu Fabra). Those algorithms were designed to detect defects in long audio streams, however, this thesis aims to be able to detect defects in much shorter audio files.
- The second one is to create and develop algorithms to detect other common issues in sound files. Three more issues will be evaluated in this thesis, low SNR, bit depth discrepancies and sample rate discrepancies.

Low SNR (Signal to Noise Ratio) signals are defined by the SNR equation, which quantifies the relationship between the desired (S) and undesired (N) part of the waveform. These signals will have a noise (or unwanted) content higher than desired compared to the desired signal itself.

The other two defects are considered to be in the same group of audio defects which are the resolution issues: bit depth and sample rate discrepancies.

These kind of sounds have a certain tonality and users might be interested in knowing these features. The main reason for classifying this defect is that memory is wasted in containing no relevant information.

When an audio signal is recorded at a lower sample rate than the sample rate of its container, some bandwidth remains unused because of the Nyquist limit. An extensive explanation on effective bandwidth, Nyquist limit and bit codification can be found on [11]. Some previous work on this field can be found on Geoffroy Peeters' paper [6] where a method to calculate the harmonic cutoff frequency which can be extrapolated to the effective bandwidth of a signal is introduced.

- The third objective is to evaluate those algorithms in a subset from Freesound [2]. Freesound is a collaborative repository of audio samples started in 2005 at the Music Technology Group (MTG) of Universitat Pompeu Fabra. The aim of the project was to create an open database of sounds that could also be used for scientific research. A small portion of this database will be used for the evaluation of the algorithms.

1.2 Structure of the Report

The report will be split into the state of the art, where the algorithms of will be introduced and explained, the methodology where the developed algorithms will be explained in detail and the results and conclusions, where the algorithms will be evaluated and the outcome of the thesis will be explained.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

Previous work on automatic audio problems detection has been done by Pablo Alonso-Jiménez, Lluís Joglar-Ongay, Dmitry Bogdanov, Xavier Serra in their paper Automatic detection of audio problems for quality control in digital music distribution presented to the Audio Engineering Society on March 2019 in Ireland. In this paper, multiple audio defect detections were proposed as well as multiple audio defects were described of which some will be relevant as they will be adapted and evaluated in this thesis.

2.1 Phase defects

Phase defects correspond to unfavorable relationships between both channels of audio of a stereo file that can be undesirable because of the excessive memory used to store them in case that the file is mono or phase cancelation in case cancellations appear when summing both channels. In this case, the relationship that is interesting for detecting it is the linear correlation between both channels as measured by the Pearson correlation coefficient. The Pearson correlation is defined to be the division of the covariance of two signals and the product of the standard deviation of them. That means that the range of values that the coefficient can take is $[-1,1]$ where the extremes are caused by the issues that we are tracking.

- False Stereo is caused mainly by the same information being in both channels of an audio file. This can be caused by exporting a mono file as stereo in a Digital Audio Workstation (DAW) for instance and it is detected when the pearson coefficient is close to 1.
- Out of Phase Stereo is caused by a 180 degree shift between both channels of an audio file. This shift can be caused by multiple causes, the most common one in recordings is microphone placement. When summed into a single channel audio file (mono) some frequency components cancel due to the issue. The importance of good correlation between both channels on a stereo signal is seen in the amount of articles that explain the importance of phase correlation meters in audio design and audio mixing workflows. Some examples of those articles include [3] [4].

2.2 Silence defects

Having too much silence at the start or the end of the file can also be considered a problem as information with no valuable content is being stored. For the detection of this issue the authors propose a frame by frame analysis computation of the rectified envelope to find the last silent frame at the start of the file and the first silent frame at the end of the file.

2.3 Noise bursts defects

Noise bursts are characterized by a succession of artifactual samples, typically originated in the codification process of an audio file and are part of the group that the authors denote as digital audio artifacts and that are defined by a succession of

samples that do not correspond to a realistic sound.

The detection of this issue is done by thresholding the peaks of the second derivative of the of the signal. The threshold is not fixed but rather computed using an exponential moving average (EMA) filter over the quadratic mean value of the second derivative of the input frame.

2.4 Humming defects

Humming is characterized by a low frequency (50-80Hz), steady, narrowband electrical noise added to the signal. This defect is very common in analog recording and mixing gear, as it is in the neighbourhood of the frequency of the electrical supply (50-60Hz). The authors use an algorithm proposed by Brandt and Bitzer in their paper “Automatic detection of hum in audio signals” [5] where they propose an approach based on the computation of measuring the steadiness of the frequency bins on 10-30 seconds audio segments.

2.5 Click defects

Click defects are included in the previously mentioned digital audio artifacts. They are characterized by impulsive noise that can come from multiple sources such as plosive sounds or codification errors. To detect this artifacts, after LPC algorithms are used to define the stationary part of the waveform, this is subtracted from the audio signal to then compute a peak thresholding of the output of a matched filter of that error signal.

2.6 Clipping defects

Clipping is a phenomenon given by an audio waveform exceeding the dynamic range of the media, it being the digital or the analog domain. However, we are focusing on

the digital domain, where clipping is perceived when surpassed the $[-1, 1]$ range of the values. This can be originated from DAC not having enough dynamic range to represent the signal that is passed as an input or because of badly executed limiting in mastering [6].

The method proposed by the authors is detecting streams of adjacent samples that have very little variance between them and computing an energy threshold in order to avoid silence to be detected as clipping.

2.7 Bit depth defects

Digital audio represents analog signals but in order to be able to be stored in digital media needs to be quantised both in time axis and in the amplitude axis [7]. The amplitude axis is coded with a number of bytes which will determine the number of discrete amplitude levels a sample can have.

2.8 Sample Rate defects or Bandwidth defects

This defect is directly tied to the time axis sampling described in [7]. The number of samples of the analog signal that are captured in a second in order to be able to reconstruct correctly the signal in the analog domain is the sample rate. The Sample Rate also affects the maximum analog frequency that a digital signal is able to represent as described by the Nyquist Frequency [8].

Chapter 3

Methodology

For the evaluation and creation of the algorithms, python3 was used and the code for the project can be found on ¹. For the scope of the project there were 3 algorithms developed.

3.1 Bit depth defects detection

The proposed bit depth detection algorithm works by finding the discrepancy between the value in the header of the WAV container file [9] and the extracted information from the data in it.

The byte rate is obtained from the bytes 28 to 31 of the header and then is converted following 3.1.

$$BR = \frac{b}{8} * fs = B * fs \quad (3.1)$$

Where BR is the byte rate, b is the number of bits with which the signal is coded, B is the number of bytes and fs is the sampling frequency or sampling rate. From there, the first value is obtained.

The second value for the comparison is obtained by computing the used bits in the samples of the audio file.

Samples in a PCM sound format are stored in hexadecimal values, which range from

¹<https://www.github.com/pirulok02/MTG-Audio-Problems-Detection>

0xFFFF to 0x0000 in samples coded in 16 bits. Each pair of values correspond to a byte of information and thus each value corresponds to 4 bits.

The first step in the algorithm is to divide the audio file in chunks of N samples and randomly select M of them (N and M being parameters in the algorithm, depending on the degree of confidence desired, they default to 100). Then all those values are converted to binary following 1. So that for example, two samples of 0x0AF0

Table 1: Hexadecimal to binary equivalence

Hex	Binary
0	0000
1	0001
2	0010
3	0011
4	0100
5	0101
6	0110
7	0111
8	1000
9	1001
A	1010
B	1011
C	1100
D	1101
E	1110
F	1111

and 0xFF20 will be translated in 0000 1010 1111 0000 and 1111 1111 0010 0000 respectively.

After the hex to bin conversion, an “or” operation is performed to detect which bits are never used. In the example mentioned before, the result of the operation would be 1111 1111 1111 0000. As a little endian configuration is used to read the values, the lower bits are used but from the 16 bits used to code the samples, 4 bits remain

unused thus meaning that coding the samples with 12 bits would be such as effective. However, only the higher weight unused bits contribute to the count of unused bits as the bits of lower weight are needed to represent the values of the higher values.

3.2 Bandwidth defect detection

The proposed bandwidth defect detection algorithm is based in the same principle than the bit depth detection: the discrepancy between the information stored in the header and the information extracted from the data.

The header information is retrieved from the bytes 24 to 27. After this, it is compared to the extracted frequency from the data.

To extract the information, a frame by frame analysis is done. From each frame, the most likely cutoff frequency is computed (defining the cut frequency as the last bin with relevant information). From the available frames, a histogram is computed and the most probable frequency is taken as the result and a confidence value is also computed from the histogram.

The most likely bin per each frame is computed using 3.2:

Figure 1: Flowchart for BW detection

$$Fc = \max(Fc \text{ where } \frac{1}{Fc} \sum_{i=Fc}^N FFT(x_{frame} * w_N)[i] > sumThreshold \text{ where } Fc = 0, 1, \dots, N) \quad (3.2)$$

Which value and function were obtained by trying different functions that gave a stable value which to threshold. Once the cut frequency is computed in each frame, a weighted histogram is computed where instead of simply counting the number of occurrences for each frequency bin, the energy of the frame was added so that the equation results in 3.3

$$hist[f] = \sum_{i=0}^{N_{frames}} \sum_{j=0}^N (frame_i[j])^2 \text{ for } i \text{ so that } f_i = f \quad (3.3)$$

Where Nframes is the number of frames, N is the frame size, f is the cut frequency, fi is the extracted frequency for that frame and hist[f] is the histogram array in the index f. From that weighted histogram, the most likely frequency is taken by extracting the index for which the histogram is largest. $Fc = \text{argmax}(\text{hist})$ and the confidence is extracted in two different ways depending on the value of Fc:

From there, if the confidence value is greater than a determined threshold, defaulted to 0.8 and Fc is lower than $0.85 * (N/2 + 1)$ it is considered to have a problem. However, this methodology only has been explored with a frame size of 256 samples and a hop size of 128 at the moment.

3.3 Low SNR defect detection

The low SNR detection algorithm is based on the well known SNR formula of 3.4

$$SNR = \frac{S}{N} \quad (3.4)$$

But as the signal and the noise component of this expression, are mixed in our case, a per frame classification algorithm based on the features of energy and correlation was used with the following conditions: If a frame's energy is less than a 10% of the energy the frame is classified as noise. If it is higher, the next evaluation is performed. When evaluating the correlation, the goal was to measure the resemblance of the

frame to white noise. To do this, autocorrelation was used to compute it.

Figure 2: Autocorrelation comparison of $N(0,1)$ noise and a more deterministic signal

Figure 2 represents an autocorrelation plot for white noise $N(0,1)$ and the plot below corresponds to an almost pure harmonic sound with some noise added to it. This raises the question if a measure of which percentage of the values lands in the sample in the middle is a good fit for a measure of similarity, which in further testing it is found that it is. The mathematical expressions for the computation to get the value for deciding on which kind of frame we are looking at is 3.5.

$$\begin{aligned}
 R_{xx}[l] &= \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x[n]x[n-l] \\
 ac[i] &= \frac{R_{xx}[0]}{\sum |R_{xx}[l]|} \text{ for } i = 0, 1, \dots, N_{frames} \\
 ac &= \frac{ac}{\max(|ac|)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

This ac vector of values will give us a value between 0 and 1 for each frame which is then thresholded and if the value is lower than the threshold it is considered signal, and noise otherwise. From there, once the frames are classified, the power for each signal and noise frames are added and then the SNR is computed. A problem is detected if the SNR is higher than a threshold.

3.4 Manual annotation and Grid Search

The algorithms will be evaluated against a database and a grid search will be used to find parameters that optimise the results. In order to do that, a ground truth is needed so the dataset will need to be annotated manually to create that ground truth. To execute this task, a script has been developed to automate the process.

The script has been developed in python3 and taking advantage of the *threading* built-in package each audio file in a folder was loaded, played and at the same time, the waveform and spectrum are displayed so that the user can decide which defects are present on the file and then annotates it by terminal. The script for that is in the Evaluation folder in the github repository ².

The results for the annotation are available in `"/Evaluation/Results/"` and in [10]. The results are stored in csv format where the columns are the defects and the rows are the files in the folder. For each file and each defect, a boolean is stored in the form "True" or "False".

Once the ground truth has been computed, the grid search is done by evaluating the binary outcome of the desired algorithm with a particular set of parameters and then compare the binary output to the ground truth to calculate the true positives, true negatives, false positives and false negatives and from those values the evaluation explained in the next section is done.

²<https://www.github.com/pirulok02/MTG-Audio-Problems-Detection>

Chapter 4

Results

The algorithms have been evaluated with 1120 mono sounds from the test dataset for the Kaggle [11] Audio tagging competition created by the MTG and Freesound. The test set for the dataset is an accurate representation of the content of the whole dataset for the competition. The dataset has been manually annotated by the author using the script `evaluation.py` in the Evaluation folder on the github repository. The evaluation was carried by annotating the existence of the following problems: Hum, Clicks, Noise Bursts, Saturation and Silence. Other algorithms that had to be evaluated were related to Phase issues. However, as the dataset is formed exclusively of mono files, the algorithms were not properly evaluated.

The parameter values evaluated for each algorithm will be evaluated with 3 measures: precision 4.1, recall 4.2 and $F_{0.5}$ score 4.3. A value of $\beta = 0.5$ was chosen to weight the score in favor of the precision score.

$$Precision = \frac{TruePositive}{TruePositive + FalsePositive} \quad (4.1)$$

$$Recall = \frac{TruePositive}{TruePositive + FalseNegative} \quad (4.2)$$

$$F_{\beta} = (1 + \beta^2) \frac{\textit{precision} \cdot \textit{recall}}{\beta^2 \cdot \textit{precision} + \textit{recall}}, F_{0.5} = 1.25 \frac{\textit{precision} \cdot \textit{recall}}{0.25 \cdot \textit{precision} + \textit{recall}} \quad (4.3)$$

4.1 Clicks detection evaluation

Four parameters for the `essentia` clicks detector algorithm were evaluated: `detectionThreshold`, `order`, `powerEstimationThreshold`, `silenceThreshold`. The first parameter is `detectionThreshold`, which is based on the instant power of the noisy excitation signal plus `detectionThreshold` dBs. The results are as seen in 3. The next parameter to be evaluated is `order`, which is the number of LPC coefficients to use. The results can be seen in 4. The next parameter to be evaluated is `powerEstimationThreshold`. In the algorithm, the noisy excitation is clipped to `powerEstimationThreshold` times its median. The results can be seen in 5. The next parameter to be evaluated is `silenceThreshold`. The value represents the threshold to skip silent frames. The results can be seen in 6.

Table 2: Clicks detection evaluation results

parameter name	values	value for max F-score	F-score
detection threshold	[0, 5, 10, ..., 35]	25	~0.35
order	[2, 4, 6, ..., 38]	24	~0.4
power estimation threshold	[2, 4, 6, ..., 14]	10	~0.35
silence threshold	[-70, -60, ..., -10]	-60	~0.35

4.2 Noise bursts detection evaluation

For the noise bursts detection algorithm two values were swept: `alpha` value and `threshold`. The `alpha` value is the `alpha` value for Exponential Moving Average threshold estimation. The results can be seen in 7. The `threshold` value represents the threshold to skip silent frames. The results can be seen in 8.

Table 3: Noise Bursts detection evaluation results

parameter name	values	value for max F-score	F-score
alpha	[0.1, 0.2, ..., 0.9]	0.1	~0.1
threshold	[-10, -8, ..., 10]	4	~0.3

4.3 Saturation detection evaluation

For the saturation evaluation, the parameters differentialThreshold, energyThreshold and minimumDuration. The first parameter represents minimum difference between contiguous samples of the salturated regions. The results can be seen in 9. The second parameter is energyThreshold which is the minimum energy for the algorithm to assume a region as saturated. The results can be seen in 10. The last parameter is minimumDuration, which is the time threshold for the algorithm to detect a saturated region. The results can be seen in 11.

Table 4: Saturation detection evaluation results

parameter name	values	value for max F-score	F-score
differentialThreshold	[0.001, 0.005, 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5, 1, 5, 10]	5	~0.55
energyThreshold	[-30, -20, -10, -7, -5, -3, -1, -0.01]	-5	~0.58
minimumDuration	[0.001, 0.005, 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5, 1]	0.001	~0.45

4.4 Hum detection evaluation

Four parameters of the essentia Hum algorithm were considered in the evaluation: TimeWindow, minimumDuration, NumberofHarmonics and timeContinuity. The timeWindow parameter is a measure of the analysis time to use in the Hum estimation in s. The results can be seen in 12The next parameter to be evaluated is minimumDuration, which is the minimum time span for which the hum is detected. The results can be seen in 13.The next parameter to be evaluated is NumberofHarmonics, number of harmonic components for which the algorithm will look for it to consider a humming frequency. The results can be seen in 14.The next parameter

to be evaluated is `timeContinuity`, the minimum time for a humming frequency to be present to be detected. The results can be seen in 15.

Table 5: Hum detection evaluation results

parameter name	values	value for max F-score	F-score
<code>TimeWindow</code>	[0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 1, 3, 5]	NA	NA
<code>minimumDuration</code>	[0.01, 0.07, 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 1, 3, 5]	NA	NA
<code>NumberofHarmonics</code>	[1, 2, 3, 4, 5]	NA	NA
<code>timeContinuity</code>	[0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 1, 3, 5]	NA	NA

4.5 Silence detection evaluation

For the silence detection algorithm, two parameters were evaluated: `frameSize` and `threshold`. The framesize is the number of samples per frame that the silence detection algorithm uses. The results can be seen on 16. The threshold is the threshold for deciding if a frame is silent or not. The results can be seen on 17

Table 6: Silence detection evaluation results

parameter name	values	value for max F-score	F-score
<code>frameSize</code>	[32, 64, 128, 256, 512]	NA	NA
<code>threshold</code>	[-100, -90, ..., -10]	NA	NA

4.6 BW problems detection evaluation

For the bandwidth problems detection algorithm proposed in this thesis, two parameters were evaluated: `sumThreshold` and `confTh`. `sumThreshold` is a parameter in equation 3.2 in section 3.2. As described in the same section, in order to make a binary decision, the confidence value is thresholded to a value, which is `confTh`. The results for the parameter evaluation for this algorithm can be found in 19 and 18.

Table 7: BW problems detection evaluation results

parameter name	values	value for max F-score	F-score
sumThreshold	[1e-7, 5e-7, 1e-6, 5e-6, 1e-5, 5e-5, 1e-4, 5e-4]	5e-6	~0.57
ConfTh	[0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9]	0.6	~0.53

4.7 Bit depth problems evaluation

On the chosen dataset, after the manual annotation carried by the author, no bit depth detection can be seen in any of the files. That causes for the algorithm not to have an objective evaluation as, if it was to be computed, similar results to the hum detection algorithm or silence detection algorithm would have been found.

4.8 SNR problems evaluation

For the SNR problems evaluation three parameters were evaluated: nrgThreshold, acThreshold and snrThreshold. NrgThreshold and acThreshold are the values that will decide if a frame is classified as noise or signal as described in 3.3. The results for the evaluation of these parameters can be found on 20 and 21. In the same section is also mentioned that in order to make a binary decision, the SNR value has to be thresholded to the value of snrThreshold. The results of the evaluation of this parameter can be seen in 22.

Table 8: SNR problems detection evaluation results

parameter name	values	value for max F-score	F-score
nrgThreshold	[0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9]	0.3	~0.27
acThreshold	[0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9]	0.3	~0.37
snrThreshold	[-3, -1, 1, 3, 5, 7, 9]	9	~0.35

Chapter 5

Conclusions

After the grid search results, the project has to conclude with a result that has been not satisfactory and maybe due to the time set to deliver the thesis hasn't been explored as in-depth as it should have been. After seeing the accuracies of all the algorithms being so low and, after a manual re-inspection of the audios that were detected or not as problematic, I can almost certainly state that with a most accurate ground truth (the ground truth was a manual annotation of the author), the results would be more convincing. The algorithms themselves perform fairly well when evaluated in some cherry picked audio files, however, when executed in the whole dataset there were some issues that should be revised in a later revision of the project:

- The whole dataset being mono audio files means that the phase issues have not been able to be evaluated.
- Some algorithms gave unsatisfying results such as hum and silence, a further exploration of the algorithms should be done to modify them as the use case for the algorithms and the use case for the project differ considerably.
- The annotation for the dataset used in the grid search in the results section did not prove to be a reliable ground truth upon further investigation.

The project was a good first approach to a general purpose audio problems detection investigation. However, because of a lack of objective and reliable evaluation, this can only be stated as a subjective evaluation of the author, who, upon further review of some of the files with problems detected, can ensure that the accuracy for the algorithms developed and the algorithms evaluated was more than satisfactory when reviewing the audio files manually.

List of Figures

1	Flowchart for BW detection	9
2	Autocorrelation comparison of $N(0,1)$ noise and a more deterministic signal	11
3	detectionThreshold parameter sweep results	24
4	order parameter sweep results	25
5	powerEstimationThreshold parameter sweep results	25
6	silenceThreshold parameter sweep results	26
7	alpha parameter sweep results	26
8	threshold parameter sweep results	27
9	differentialThreshold parameter sweep results	27
10	energyThreshold parameter sweep results	28
11	minimumDuration parameter sweep results	28
12	timeWindow parameter sweep results	29
13	minimumDuration parameter sweep results	29
14	numberHarmonics parameter sweep results	30
15	timeContinuity parameter sweep results	30
16	frameSize parameter sweep results	31
17	threshold parameter sweep results	31
18	threshold parameter sweep results	32
19	sumThreshold parameter sweep results	32
20	acThreshold parameter sweep results	33
21	nrgThreshold parameter sweep results	33
22	snrThreshold parameter sweep results	34

List of Tables

1	Hexadecimal to binary equivalence	8
2	Clicks detection evaluation results	14
3	Noise Bursts detection evaluation results	15
4	Saturation detection evaluation results	15
5	Hum detection evaluation results	16
6	Silence detection evaluation results	16
7	BW problems detection evaluation results	17
8	SNR problems detection evaluation results	17

Bibliography

- [1] Essentia, an open-source library and tools for audio and music analysis, description and synthesis. <https://essentia.upf.edu/documentation/>.
- [2] Freesound,. <https://freesound.org/>.
- [3] H. robjohns, what are my phase-correlation meters telling me? <https://www.soundonsound.com/sound-advice/q-what-are-my-phase-correlation-meters-telling-me>. 2016, Retrieved February 7, 2019.
- [4] D. keller. learn how to identify and correct phase issues in your mixes.,. <https://www.uaudio.com/blog/understanding-audio-phase/>.
- [5] Brandt, M. & Bitzer, J. Automatic detection of hum in audio signals. *J. Audio Eng. Soc* **62**, 584–595 (2014). URL <http://www.aes.org/e-lib/browse.cfm?elib=17388>.
- [6] Clipping(audio) - wikipedia. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Clipping_\(audio\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Clipping_(audio)). Edited: 2019-08-20.
- [7] Zölzer, U. *Digital Audio Signal Processing Second Edition* (2008).
- [8] Wikipedia - nyquist frequency. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nyquist_frequency.
- [9] Wikipedia - waveform audio format,. https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Waveform_Audio_Format.

-
- [10] Victor badenas, dataset annotation. <https://zenodo.org/deposit?page=1&size=20>.
- [11] Freesound audio tagging 2019, automatically recognize sounds and apply tags of varying natures. <https://www.kaggle.com/c/freesound-audio-tagging-2019>.

Appendix A

First Appendix: Grid Search F-score, accuracy and recall

Figure 3: detectionThreshold parameter sweep results

Figure 4: order parameter sweep results

Figure 5: powerEstimationThreshold parameter sweep results

Figure 6: silenceThreshold parameter sweep results

Figure 7: alpha parameter sweep results

Figure 8: threshold parameter sweep results

Figure 9: differentialThreshold parameter sweep results

Figure 10: energyThreshold parameter sweep results

Figure 11: minimumDuration parameter sweep results

Figure 12: timeWindow parameter sweep results

Figure 13: minimumDuration parameter sweep results

Figure 14: numberHarmonics parameter sweep results

Figure 15: timeContinuity parameter sweep results

Figure 16: frameSize parameter sweep results

Figure 17: threshold parameter sweep results

Figure 18: threshold parameter sweep results

Figure 19: sumThreshold parameter sweep results

Figure 20: acThreshold parameter sweep results

Figure 21: nrgThreshold parameter sweep results

Figure 22: snrThreshold parameter sweep results